

TEACHING CONVERSATION IN THE ENGLISH CLASSES OF STUDENTS OF AGRARIAN UNIVERSITY

Adilova Nilufar Ahmadjonovna¹

Azizova Zilola Ravshanovna²

^{1,2}Tashkent state agrarian university,

Language department, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6169531>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th February 2022

Accepted: 10th February 2022

Online: 15th February 2022

KEY WORDS

*foreign language, colloquial
speech, lesson, teaching,
phrases*

ABSTRACT

The article considers one of the important aspects in teaching students' colloquial speech at foreign language lessons in agricultural universities. It is no coincidence that in recent years there have been numerous offline and online conversation skill courses that teach to speak English.

When preparing and conducting a presentation in a foreign language, the correct structuring of spoken language is of paramount importance. As you know, the ideal speech consists of three parts: the introduction, the main part of the speech and the conclusion, each of which implements certain intentions of the speaker in English and includes stereotypical speech formulas. Therefore, it is necessary to teach students to correctly use the speech formulas of business communication, depending on the presentation stage and speech intentions. For example, many phrases belong to such clichéd forms of colloquial speech.

The main task of any colloquial speech in English is to have an impact on the audience. In order to form students' skills to establish contact and exert the necessary influence on communication

partners in the process of speaking in English, it seems necessary to introduce certain syntactic constructions and stylistic devices into the content of training.

An important component of the content of teaching foreign language skills is textual material. At the same time, the types of texts used should correlate with certain types of colloquial speech in English.

Cultural information also acts as one of the components of the content of teaching foreign language presentation skills and abilities, which ensures adequate competence of students and their knowledge related to the specifics of preparing and conducting colloquial speech in English by representatives of different business communities.

An equally important area in teaching business communication in a

foreign language is the work on the formation of debating skills and abilities that allow future specialists to participate in various international conferences, scientific symposiums, negotiations with foreign colleagues.

For a successful discussion, students must have a good understanding of the structural organization of the discussion and be able to identify its stages, taking into account the specifics of the discussion intentions of both the moderator and the participants in the discussion. The discussion consists of five main stages:

1. the beginning of the discussion
2. the main conversation
3. discussion
4. summing up
5. the end of the discussion.

Depending on the stage of the discussion, as well as the role function, the student chooses the type of communicative act in which his discussion intentions are realized.

The communicative act underlies any speech interaction; therefore, when forming the ability to conduct a discussion in a foreign language, we must necessarily rely on the communicative act as the main element in the formation of foreign language interaction skills. Therefore, the main element of the content of teaching such skills should be a set of communicative acts characteristic of such an interactive speech event as a discussion.

The most typical discussion intentions are the following: to discuss any issue in order to make a decision; convince a partner of something; express/defend your opinion; support / refute the partner's opinion; put forward and justify your proposal; generalize; to make a

conclusion; express doubt, criticism on the issue under discussion. These discussion intentions are realized in communicative acts of evaluating and commenting on information, organizing speech and achieving understanding, regulating the actions of partners in interaction. At different stages of the discussion, a different set of communicative acts is used.

Verbal means signaling the type of a communicative act are communication means - stereotypical speech formulas that allow participants in the interaction to control the course of speech interaction. The list of communication means is extensive, but we propose to include only a part of them as a component of the content of professional interaction training, namely, the speech formulas used in the discussion.

The analysis of authentic interactive texts made it possible to identify the intentional specificity of the "leader" and "participants" of the discussion, which is reflected in the speech clichés noted in this situation. As a rule, the discussions do not go smoothly, the proposals are often repeated, reformulated with clarification of the ways and details of solving the problem, and the participants are so absorbed in their own proposals that they do not follow the progress of the discussion as a whole. The task of the facilitator is to record the main points and results of the discussion of the problem and find ways to solve it. Speech formulas for controlling the discussion reflect all its stages - 1) beginning with the announcement of the topic and work plan, 2) main speech, 3) discussion, 4) summing up and 5) making a decision and ending the discussion. The intentional specificity of the "participants"

of the discussion is much more diverse, since they have to take the floor, express their opinion, agree and disagree, interrupt, convince, give advice, emphasize, generalize.

When developing interactive skills and abilities to control the discussion, the stylistic adequacy of communication means is of particular importance, which can be manifested in the intensity of their impact. We single out neutral, strong and weak influence verbalized by a certain set of communication means. These are the main

components of the content of teaching debating skills.

The need to form foreign language presentation and discussion skills and abilities is dictated by modern requirements for the professional language training of students, which are due to the growing demand of our society for graduates who are able to independently, without the help of an interpreter, quickly and competently solve professional problems.

References

1. Khakimova M. F., Mirzaeva M. N., Bazarova U. M., Musakhanova G. M. Opportunities of innovation technologies in higher education. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 3, 12 (Dec. 2020), 282-285. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v3i12.1002>.
2. U. Bazarova, S. Suyarova Development formation of professional competence and moral education system for students of universities // *Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka*, 2021
3. Bazarova U.M. The Role of Spiritual and Moral Education of Students of Technical University in the Lessons of Foreign Languages. // Philadelphia, USA-2019.-614-616s.
4. Bazarova U.M. The state of the problem of moral and aesthetic education of students by means of a foreign language at the present stage // *International scientific journal "Scientific Horizons" No. 1 / Moscow 2019*
5. I.A. Sharipova [Efficiency of interactive methods of teaching a professionally-oriented English language for students of a technical university](#) // *Theoretical & Applied Science*, 2019
6. I.A. Sharipova [Didactic games on English language classes as a means of developing professionally significant qualities of a future specialist](#) // *Научные горизонты № 1(17) | 2019*
7. M. J. Ashirmatova Terminology at the Agrarian University in Russian // *International scientific journal Theoretical and practical science // Philadelphia, USA -2021-№ 1.-P. 201-203*
8. Ashirmatova M.D. [Methodology formation and system of communication ability of university students in the classes of the Russian language](#) [Электронный ресурс] // *Мировая наука.-2021.- №10(55) (10.2021)*.